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Possibilities of Using Financial Technologies in the Modern Financial Market

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***Abstract:** The article examines the advantages and disadvantages of using financial technologies in the modern financial market. characteristics and types of robo-advisors are explored. Investment portfolio management opportunities through robo-advisors have been analyzed.*

***Key words:** Digital finance, robo-advisors, securities, investment portfolio, share, bond, investor, issuer.*

INTRODUCTION

Effective diversification of the investment portfolio is one of the most important tasks for investors who are the main participants of the financial market. Based on the investor's strategy, they can be divided into three groups. An "aggressive" investor is prepared for a high level of risk while looking for high returns. The group of "Moderate or balanced" investors strives to achieve a balance between risk and profitability indicators. A "conservative" investor, on the other hand, tries to make a profit based on a relatively low probability of loss. Therefore, each investor differs according to the value of his portfolio, level of readiness for risk, strategic and tactical goals. Based on these characteristics, investors form their portfolios.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Nowadays, the use of financial technology advances in creating and managing an investment portfolio is becoming popular. In this regard, robo-advisors, which are products of artificial intelligence, have already become assistants to investors.

Robo-advisors offer financial advisory services to participants who want to invest in the financial market, and manage investments by minimizing human intervention. They provide digital financial advice based on mathematical rules or algorithms and provide investment portfolio management services.

Robo-advisors are widely used in the financial market as competitors to mutual funds. Robo-advisors serve these investors as mechanized platforms that use automated algorithms to provide financial advice. Robo-advisors are more user-friendly and cost-effective than traditional financial advisors, and are more risk-adjusted..

In the robo-advisor segment, private investors can choose investment volumes based on their size and risk appetite, and robo-advisors offer automated online portfolios. These platforms are especially preferred for investors who cannot or do not want to constantly monitor their investment portfolio. Such automated investment services can be evaluated as a good opportunity for those who have little initial capital and want to get high returns without inherent investment risks.

Robo-advisory platforms use an online survey to collect information from clients about their financial situation, risk level, and future goals, and then use the data to provide advice and automatically invest the client's assets.

The global market for robo-advisors was valued at USD 13.6 billion in 2020 and is expected to reach USD 36.6 billion by 2026, showing a CAGR of 22.0% from 2021 to 2026. There were 8.7 million users of robo-advisory services worldwide in 2020, and 15.5 million users are expected by the end of 2023. By 2027, this figure will reach 234.30 million users. Assets under management in Robo-Advisors market is projected to reach \$2.76 trillion in 2023 and \$4.66 trillion by 2027.¹

New clients who sign up for robo-advisor services first fill out an online survey and provide basic information about their financial goals. Questions may include items on risk tolerance, financial timeline and goals, income, liabilities, savings, and current investments. With the information gathered, the robo-advisor creates a profile of the investor and uses an algorithm to predict the best portfolio allocation the investor should make. A robo-advisor regularly monitors and rebalances a portfolio of investments based on market volatility and changes in the investor's goals and risk tolerance. Through artificial intelligence technology, a robo-advisor analyzes data from an individual's financial transactions to understand their financial behavior. In addition, it analyzes investment, banking and credit card transactions, allowing robo-advisors to develop a personalized portfolio that matches their investment goals.

The following were recognized as the best robo-advisors in 2023 ²:

1. The best overall robo-advisor is Betterment
2. The best robo-advisor for those just starting to invest is Vanguard Digital Advisor
3. Best robo-advisor for high balance- Vanguard Personal Advisor Services. The minimum account limit starts at \$50,000.
4. The robo-advisor with the lowest management fees is SoFi Automated Investing. There is no commission if the minimum balance starts at \$1.
5. The best robo-advisor for financial planning is Wealthfront

CONCLUSIONS

Each financial market participant should choose robo-advisory platforms based on their investment goals. As these platforms provide consulting services on financial planning along with investment portfolio management, they also provide an opportunity to receive advice from a professional expert,

¹ <https://www.statista.com/outlook/dmo/fintech/digital-investment/robo-advisors/worldwide>

² <https://www.forbes.com/advisor/investing/best-robo-advisors/>

and for this, there are separate fee definitions. Therefore, when choosing a robo-advisor, it is appropriate to study their features.

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